

DREAM PROJECT

Public website, collaborative platform

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Writers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Léa Vilcocq (CNRS) - Sivane Mosenego (CNRS) 	
People involved in the deliverable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Laurent Djakovitch (CNRS) - Marlène Fabre ... - Laurence Besson ... - Isabelle Raux Monfray ... 	
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Summary	As the DREAM project started on April 1 st 2024, several tools have been set up or are currently in creation to ensure the communication between the partners of the project and to communicate about the project. For the internal communication, a collaborative platform is available for all partners to work together and share documents. For the external communication, several tools will be available to promote the project and disseminate its results.	

Introduction

The DREAM project will be promoted with different communication and dissemination tools during the whole duration of the project. In order to ensure a good cooperation between the organizations involved in the project, a collaborative platform will be used for all partners to work together and share their work with the consortium.

1. Collaborative platform

A collaborative platform has been set up for the consortium to work together and share documents, results and other information. The collaborative platform is available for consortium members with the following link: <https://extra.core-cloud.net/projets/dream-project/default.aspx>. The platform is based on the CoRe service developed by CNRS and based on Sharepoint software. Data are stored on a Cloud in France in a secure way. In the collaborative platform, the DREAM consortium has access to various tools:

- Contact: a contact list with all consortium members is available on the collaborative platform,
- Documents: consortium members have access to documents related to the DREAM project on the collaborative platform, like the Grant Agreement or deliverables of the project in the future. The consortium members also have the possibility to upload documents on the collaborative platform so the rest of the consortium has access to the documents.
- Tasks: the tool gives the timeline of the project separated in work packages, tasks, deliverables and milestones with all due dates and a visual timeline.
- Calendar: the tool gives the opportunity of having a shared calendar with the whole consortium. This possibility is useful to inform the dates of meetings related to the project and to share information about the meetings (for example, links for online meetings).
- Newsfeed: all consortium members are able to publish messages to the rest of the consortium on the collaborative platform.

Since all members of the DREAM consortium won't have the same involvement in the project realization, there is a possibility to choose different forms of access to the platform. All members of the consortium working on the project for a significant period of time will have an unrestricted access, allowing them to view and download the documents and to share, upload and modify documents. Members of the consortium working on the project for a short period (for example interns in the partner organizations) will have a restricted access to the platform, allowing them to view and download the documents.

The following screenshot shows the home page of the DREAM collaborative platform:

Figure 1 : Homepage of the DREAM collaborative platform

2. DREAM Website

A public website for the promotion and dissemination of the DREAM project is currently being created. The hosting of the website was found and the website is being created but is not yet available for public. The website will be available with the following URL : dream.cnrs.fr.

To mark the beginning of the project, a short information has been published on a CNRS regional newsletter “CNRS Hebdo” (<https://www.cnrs.fr/CNRS-Hebdo/rhone-auvergne/Lettre/397/Lettre.aspx>) and on the CP2M website (<https://www.cp2m.org/research/13-dream-project.html>).

3. Creation of a logo

A logo for the DREAM project was created to build a visual identity for the project. This logo will be visible on all communications concerning the DREAM project and will help identifying the project on websites, posters, publications etc. Below is the DREAM logo (Figure 2):

Figure 2 : DREAM logo

4. Social media

In order to promote the DREAM project to a larger public, it will be present on social media. A LinkedIn page has been created to ensure a bigger visibility of the project. Members of the consortium follow the DREAM project LinkedIn page, which will be useful to promote its publications. Figure 4 shows the number of visitors of the LinkedIn page. The augmentation is explained by the promotion of the LinkedIn page among the consortium.

Figure 3 : LinkedIn page of the DREAM project

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe program under the grant agreement N°101130523.

Figure 4 : Evolution of the visitors on the LinkedIn page of the DREAM project.

Conclusion

The communication & dissemination tools of the project are in construction and should be finalized soon. Having these tools ready will allow the consortium to promote the project as much as possible and to disseminate the project’s work progress and results.

